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Variants of LSTM cells for single-channel speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction

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Abstract

Speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction aims at estimating the target speaker from a mixture of speakers utilizing auxiliary information about the target speaker. In this paper, we consider a single-channel target speaker extraction system consisting of a speaker embedder network and a speaker separator network. Instead of using standard long short-term memory (LSTM) cells in the separator network, we propose two variants of LSTM cells that are customized for speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction. The first variant customizes both the forget gate and input gate of the LSTM cell, aiming at retaining only relevant features related to target speaker and disregarding the interfering speakers by simultaneously resetting and updating the cell state using the speaker embedding. For the second variant, we introduce a new gate within the LSTM cell, referred to as auxiliary-modulation gate. This gate modulates the information processing during cell state reset, aiming at learning the long-term and short-term discriminative features of the target speaker. Both in unidirectional and bidirectional mode, experimental results on 2-speaker mixtures, 3-speaker mixtures, and noisy mixtures (containing 1, 2, or 3 speakers) show that both proposed variants of LSTM cells outperform the standard LSTM cells for target speaker extraction, where the best performance is obtained using the auxiliary-gated LSTM cells.

Keywords Speaker extraction, Deep neural network, Informed source separation, LSTM cells

1 Introduction

In many speech communication applications, such as videoconferencing systems, hearing aids, and smart speakers, the recorded microphone signals contain a mixture of multiple speakers and background noise. A substantial amount of research dealing with mixtures of overlapping sources has focused on blind source separation [1–3], where the aim is to extract all individual sources from the mixture. However, in many practical applications, we may be interested in only one particular source, i.e.,

the target speaker. In principle, this can be achieved by extracting all individual sources from the mixture using blind source separation techniques [4–11] as a first step and selecting the target speaker from the estimated sources as a second step, which is referred to as a two-step method. However, for many blind source separation techniques, the number of sources in the mixture needs to be known in advance or needs to be estimated, which is not trivial in practice. In contrast to two-step methods, several one-step methods [12–29] have been proposed which aim to directly estimate the target speaker from the mixture and do not require the number of sources to be known or estimated.

The first proposed one-step method [12] aimed at extracting the target speaker for a fixed target and interfering speaker combination. However, the speaker-pair dependency of this method relies on the availability of large amounts of data and fails to generalize for unseen speakers. More robust one-step speaker-conditioned

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methods for target speaker extraction [13–29] have been proposed, which utilize auxiliary information (e.g., reference speech [14–22], visual cues [23–25], speech activity [26], or directional information [27–29]) about the target speaker. Most speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction systems consist of two networks: an auxiliary network and a main network. The auxiliary network provides a distinctive feature about the target speaker, which guides the main network towards estimating the target speaker from the mixture. In this paper, we consider single-channel target speaker extraction and utilize reference speech of the target speaker as auxiliary information (see Fig. 1). The auxiliary network, i.e., the speaker embedder network, is used to generate the speaker embedding from the reference speech of the target speaker, while the main network, i.e., the speaker separator network, estimates the target speaker from the mixture signal.

The speaker embedder and separator networks can be trained either separately [15–18] or jointly [19–21] to perform target speaker extraction. The separator networks in [15–17] estimate a time-frequency mask, whereas the separator networks in [18–21] estimate the target speaker from the mixture in the time domain. Due to the time-frequency structure in the input signal, mask estimation in the time-frequency domain often requires less complex network architectures compared to target speaker extraction in the time domain. Additionally, it enables the speaker extraction system to naturally capture both temporal and frequency components. Therefore, in this work, we focus on mask estimation in the time-frequency domain.

Different combinations of network architectures have been investigated for both networks. The embedder networks in [15, 16, 18] utilize the same LSTM-based pre-trained speaker identification system [30], while a different LSTM-based architecture has been utilized in [19] and ResNet-based embedder networks have been utilized in [17, 20, 21]. The separator networks in [15, 16] utilize a convolutional long short-term memory

(CNN-LSTM) architecture, while an attention-based architecture has been utilized in [17] and different temporal convolutional neural network (TCN)-based architectures have been utilized in [18, 20, 21].

Inspired by the working principle of LSTM cells [31, 32] and leveraging the success of its variants [33–35] for different applications, in this paper, we propose two different variants of LSTM cells, which are customized for speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction. These variants are to be utilized in the separator network instead of standard LSTM cells. The first proposed variant is based on our previously proposed forget gate customization [16], but instead of only customizing the forget gate, in this paper, we propose to customize both the forget gate as well as the input gate. The customization of both gates is performed to reset the cell state aiming at updating the cell state with relevant target speaker information while disregarding the other speakers. The second proposed variant is inspired by [35], where we introduce a new gate referred to as auxiliary-modulation gate. While the information processing through all gates (forget, input, and output) of the LSTM cell is initially kept unchanged, it is modulated during resetting of the cell state. The purpose of this auxiliary-modulation gate is to modulate the information of the forget and input gates, aiming at better learning the long-term and short-term discriminative features of the target speaker with the help of the corresponding speaker embedding.

This paper aims to investigate the benefits of both proposed variants of LSTM cells for target speaker extraction compared to standard LSTM cells. In order to do so, we consider a standard LSTM-based baseline system [15], where time-frequency-based embedder and separator networks are trained separately. In addition, we compare the performance of one-step target speaker extraction using the proposed variants of LSTM cells with two-step target speaker extraction. Experimental results on 2-speaker mixtures, 3-speaker mixtures, and noisy mixtures (containing 1, 2, or 3 speakers) simulated using the test set of the Librispeech

Fig. 1 Block diagram of speaker-conditioned (one-step) method for target speaker extraction

dataset [36] and the MUSAN dataset [37] show that both proposed variants of LSTM cells outperform standard LSTM cells, both in unidirectional as well as bidirectional mode. Among both proposed variants, the best performance is obtained using the auxiliary-gated LSTM cells. Besides, the results on 2-speaker mixtures also show the superior performance of both proposed variants of LSTM cells compared to two-step methods for target speaker extraction.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we discuss speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction based on LSTM cells. After introducing standard LSTM cells, we propose two customized variants of LSTM cells. In Section 3, we present the experimental setup, including the used datasets, network architectures, hyperparameters used for training and evaluation, and baseline systems. Section 4 presents the experimental results of several target speaker extraction systems.

2 Speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction

We consider a scenario where a single microphone records a mixture of I speakers and background noise. In the short-time Fourier transform (STFT) domain, the microphone signal $Y(k, l)$, with k and l denoting the frequency index and the time frame index, respectively, is given by

$$Y(k, l) = \sum_{i=1}^I X_i(k, l) + V(k, l), \quad (1)$$

where $X_i(k, l)$ denotes the speech component corresponding to the i -th speaker and $V(k, l)$ denotes the noise component. The j -th speaker is assumed to be the target speaker, with $1 \leq j \leq I$. Similar to the speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction systems in [15–17], we consider a separator network that aims at extracting the speech component $X_j(k, l)$ corresponding to the target speaker by multiplying the microphone signal with a real-valued soft mask, i.e.,

$$\hat{X}_j(k, l) = M_j(k, l)Y(k, l). \quad (2)$$

The goal of the speaker separator network is hence to estimate the mask $M_j(k, l)$ utilizing the target speaker embedding \mathbf{e}_j (see Fig. 1). Finally, the time-domain signal is reconstructed by applying the inverse STFT to $\hat{X}_j(k, l)$ in (2) using a weighted overlap-add procedure.

In the following subsections, we will discuss the considered speaker embedder and separator networks. Furthermore, we will discuss standard LSTM cells and propose two variants of LSTM cells that are customized for speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction.

2.1 Speaker embedder network

As in many speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction systems, we use a speaker identification system as the speaker embedder network. A fixed-dimensional vector representation commonly known as speaker embedding [38, 39] is utilized to distinguish between different speakers. The speaker embedding obtained from the reference speech of the target speaker is used for guiding the separator network towards estimating the target speech component from the mixture signal. In this paper, we have used an LSTM-based speaker identification system as our speaker embedder network, which is discussed in detail in Section 3.2.

2.2 Speaker separator network

The speaker separator network aims at estimating the soft mask corresponding to the target speaker utilizing the target speaker embedding. The speaker separator network in [15] uses a CNN-LSTM architecture, where first convolutional operations are performed on the STFT magnitude of the microphone signal to obtain a transformed representation \mathbf{r} . The target speaker embedding \mathbf{e}_j is then repeated and concatenated with this transformed representation along the frequency dimension and provided as input to the LSTM block for estimating the mask, i.e.,

$$M_j(k, l) = \phi(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{e}_j), \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{g}(|Y(k, l)|), \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{g}(\circ)$ denotes the convolutional operations and $\phi(\circ)$ denotes the LSTM block consisting of LSTM cells and fully connected layers. Instead of using standard LSTM cells, in this paper, we propose two variants of LSTM cells that are customized for speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction. Before discussing these variants, the working principle of the standard LSTM cell is briefly reviewed.

2.2.1 Standard LSTM cell

Figure 2 depicts a standard LSTM cell [31, 32]. The working principle of an LSTM cell depends on its cell state and three gates: the forget gate, the input gate, and the output gate. The cell state behaves like the memory of the network, having a recursive property with the ability to retain information through time, while the different gates can add or remove information at each step t . In the following, the weight matrices and the bias vectors of the forget gate, the input gate, the output gate, and the control update are denoted by \mathbf{W}_f , \mathbf{W}_i , \mathbf{W}_o , and \mathbf{W}_c and \mathbf{b}_f ,

Fig. 2 Standard LSTM cell: the input to the forget gate \mathbf{f}_t (5), input gate \mathbf{i}_t (6), and output gate \mathbf{o}_t (9) is the concatenation of the transformed representation \mathbf{r} obtained from the CNN layers and the target speaker embedding \mathbf{e}_j . σ denotes the sigmoid activation function

\mathbf{b}_i , \mathbf{b}_o , and \mathbf{b}_c , respectively. The current and previous cell states are denoted by \mathbf{c}_t and \mathbf{c}_{t-1} , while the current and previous hidden states are denoted by \mathbf{h}_t and \mathbf{h}_{t-1} .

As can be seen from (3) and Fig. 2, the input to each gate of the LSTM cell is the concatenation of the transformed representation \mathbf{r} obtained from the CNN layers and the target speaker embedding \mathbf{e}_j . The recursive property allows the LSTM cell to store information from the previous state. The forget gate of the LSTM cell decides which information should be retained or disregarded based on the previous hidden state and the current input. The information is retained in the cell state if the output of the forget gate is close to 1; otherwise, it is disregarded. The output of the forget gate is obtained as

$$\mathbf{f}_t = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_f[\mathbf{h}_{t-1}, (\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{e}_j)] + \mathbf{b}_f), \quad (5)$$

where σ denotes the sigmoid activation function.

The input gate has the ability to add new information to the cell state but can not remove any information from it. It decides which information is getting updated and stored in the cell state, and its output is obtained as

$$\mathbf{i}_t = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_i[\mathbf{h}_{t-1}, (\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{e}_j)] + \mathbf{b}_i). \quad (6)$$

The cell state behaves like the memory of the network, and is updated as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{c}}_t = \tanh(\mathbf{W}_c[\mathbf{h}_{t-1}, (\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{e}_j)] + \mathbf{b}_c), \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{c}_t = \mathbf{f}_t * \mathbf{c}_{t-1} + \mathbf{i}_t * \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_t, \quad (8)$$

where $*$ denotes point-wise multiplication.

Finally, the output gate decides which part of the cell state is transferred to the next hidden state, i.e., the output of the output gate is obtained as

$$\mathbf{o}_t = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_o[\mathbf{h}_{t-1}, (\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{e}_j)] + \mathbf{b}_o). \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_t = \mathbf{o}_t * \tanh(\mathbf{c}_t). \quad (10)$$

2.2.2 Customized LSTM cell (F+I)

With the specific goal of target speaker extraction, each LSTM cell is supposed to retain information related to the target speaker, while disregarding information unrelated to the target speaker, i.e., originating from other speakers and background noise. However, since in practice this will not be perfectly achieved, we propose customizing the LSTM cells to only retain the target speaker information by changing the information processing through both the forget gate and the input gate. Figure 3 depicts the proposed customized LSTM cell (F+I). Instead of using the concatenation of the target speaker embedding \mathbf{e}_j and the output of the CNN layers \mathbf{r} as input to the forget gate and input gate, we only use the target speaker embedding \mathbf{e}_j as input, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{f}_t = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_{ef}[\mathbf{h}_{t-1}, \mathbf{e}_j] + \mathbf{b}_{ef}), \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{i}_t = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_{ei}[\mathbf{h}_{t-1}, \mathbf{e}_j] + \mathbf{b}_{ei}), \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{W}_{ef} and \mathbf{b}_{ef} denote the weight matrix and the bias of the customized forget gate and \mathbf{W}_{ei} and \mathbf{b}_{ei} denote the weight matrix and the bias of the customized input gate. As in the standard LSTM cell, the input to the output gate is the concatenation of the transformed

Fig. 3 Proposed customized LSTM cell (F+I): the input to the forget gate f_t (11) and the input gate i_t (12) is only the target speaker embedding e_j . σ denotes the sigmoid activation function

representation r and the target speaker embedding e_j . The motivation behind the proposed customization is to enable the forget gate to retain the information related to only the target speaker, while at the same time the input gate adds and updates the same information to the cell state. Hence, it is expected that information unrelated to the target speaker (other speakers, background noise) will be disregarded from the current cell state, which affects the current hidden state and is utilized for computing the next hidden state. It should be noted that the customized LSTM cell (F+I) is an extension of the customized LSTM cell proposed in [16], where only the forget gate was customized.

2.2.3 Customized auxiliary-gated LSTM cell

Inspired by the modified LSTM cell architecture presented in [35], in the second customization, we introduce a new gate within the LSTM cell, referred to as auxiliary-modulation gate. Figure 4 depicts the proposed customized auxiliary-gated LSTM cell.

The auxiliary-modulation gate is defined as

$$a_t = \sigma(W_a[h_{t-1}, e_j] + b_a), \tag{13}$$

where W_a and b_a denote the weight matrix and the bias of the auxiliary-modulation gate. It should be noted that the input to the auxiliary-modulation gate is only the

Fig. 4 Proposed customized auxiliary-gated LSTM cell: the input denotes the concatenation of the transformed representation r obtained from the CNN layers and the target speaker embedding e_j , while the input to the auxiliary modulation gate a_t (13) is only the target speaker embedding e_j . σ denotes the sigmoid activation function

target speaker embedding \mathbf{e}_j , while the input to all other gates (forget, input, output) is the concatenation of the transformed representation \mathbf{r} and the target speaker embedding \mathbf{e}_j . The proposed auxiliary-modulation gate is part of both the forget gate and the input gate, hence leading to a direct impact on the cell state. The motivation behind this architecture is to modulate the information retained by the forget gate and the input gate by exploiting long-term and short-term discriminative features of the target speaker. After the modulation of information in the forget gate and the input gate, the cell state is updated as

$$\mathbf{c}_t = \mathbf{f}_t * \mathbf{a}_t * \mathbf{c}_{t-1} + \mathbf{i}_t * \mathbf{a}_t * \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_t. \quad (14)$$

The motivation behind the proposed customization is to retain only the information related to the target speaker in the cell state at each step, while simultaneously disregarding the information unrelated to the target speaker.

3 Experimental setup

In this section, we present the experimental setup used for all considered one-step and two-step target speaker extraction systems. In Section 3.1, we discuss the speech datasets used for training and testing. In Section 3.2 and 3.3, we discuss the network architecture and the hyperparameters for the speaker embedder and separator networks of the (one-step) speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction systems. Finally, in Section 3.4, we discuss the network architecture and the hyperparameters for two two-step methods based on blind source separation.

3.1 Speech datasets

To generate the training, validation, and test data, we have used two different speech datasets with a sampling rate of 16 kHz, namely the Voxceleb dataset [40] and the Librispeech dataset [36]. We have used the Voxceleb dataset only to train the speaker embedder network, while we have used the Librispeech dataset employed by several existing speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction systems [15–18] to train, validate and test the speaker separator network.

Voxceleb dataset [40]: this dataset consists of more than 1 million utterances from more than 7000 speakers collected from YouTube. We have used the official training and validation split of the Voxceleb dataset only for training the speaker embedder network.

Librispeech dataset [36]: this dataset consists of 1000 h of English speech with an official training, validation, and test split. The training set of the dataset is partitioned into 3 subsets, with approximate size 100 h, 360 h, and 500 h respectively. In this paper, we have only considered

the 100 h subset of training set having 251 speakers to create the training data, while the official validation and test sets, each having 40 speakers have been used to create the validation and test data, respectively. To generate 2-speaker mixtures, we have used the same procedure as in [15], namely, randomly choosing two utterances from two different speakers and mixing them at a signal-to-interference ratio (SIR) of 0 dB. One speaker is considered as the target speaker, while the other speaker as the interfering speaker. A different utterance from the target speaker is used as the reference speech to obtain the target speaker embedding. A similar procedure has been followed to generate 3-speaker mixtures, where three different speakers are randomly chosen. After mixing both interfering speakers with the same power, the resulting mixture of interfering speakers has been mixed with the target speaker at 0 dB. All together, we have generated 160 h of training data, 40 h of validation data, and 14 h of test data for both 2-speaker and 3-speaker mixtures. We have used these training and validation data to train the speaker separator networks of the one-step methods and the blind source separation networks of the two-step methods, while test data is used for testing all considered target speaker extraction systems.

3.2 Speaker embedder network

For the speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction systems, we have used the same speaker embedder network as for the baseline system [15], i.e., an LSTM-based speaker identification system proposed in [30]. The speaker embedder network consists of 3 LSTM layers, each having 768 nodes. As input features the network uses 40-dimensional log-Mel-features, which are computed using an FFT size of 512, a Hann window with a frame length of 400 samples, and a frame shift of 160 samples. Given the log-Mel-features of the reference speech of the target speaker, the speaker embedder network generates a fixed 256-dimensional embedding vector. We have retrained the speaker embedder network on the Voxceleb dataset using stochastic gradient descent and a loss function referred to as generalized end-to-end (GE2E) loss presented in [30]. We have used the same parameters as in [30], namely an initial learning rate of 0.01, a batch size of 64, and a maximum of 1000 epochs.

3.3 Speaker separator network

Similar to the baseline system [15], the separator network of the speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction systems consists of eight 2D dilated convolutional layers, an LSTM layer, and two fully connected (FC) layers. Each convolutional layer is followed by a batch-normalization layer and a ReLU activation function. The parameters of the layers are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Parameters of the separator network, consisting of eight convolutional layers, an LSTM layer (standard or customized LSTM cells), and two fully connected layers

Layer	Kernel size	Dilation	Filters/nodes
Conv1	(1×7)	(1×1)	64
Conv2	(7×1)	(1×1)	64
Conv3	(5×5)	(1×1)	64
Conv4	(5×5)	(2×1)	64
Conv5	(5×5)	(4×1)	64
Conv6	(5×5)	(8×1)	64
Conv7	(5×5)	(16×1)	64
Conv8	(1×1)	(1×1)	8
LSTM	-	-	600
FC 1	-	-	514
FC 2	-	-	257

The STFT magnitude of the microphone signal in (4) is computed using an FFT size of 512, a square-root Hann window with a frame length of 512 samples, and a frame shift of 256 samples.

In total, we have trained 8 different separator networks, depending on the LSTM cells used in the LSTM layer and whether unidirectional or bidirectional mode is considered:

- *Standard LSTM/BLSTM*: retrained baseline system [15] using standard LSTM cells
- *Customized LSTM/BLSTM (F)*: baseline system presented in [16] where customization was only performed in the forget gate
- *Customized LSTM/BLSTM (F+I)*: proposed system using customized LSTM cells (F+I) described in Section 2.2.2

- *Customized auxiliary-gated LSTM/BLSTM*: proposed system using customized auxiliary-gated LSTM cells described in Section 2.2.3

All separator networks have been trained using the scale-invariant signal-to-distortion ratio (SI-SDR) loss function [9] and the Adam optimizer [41] with a learning rate of 0.0002. We have used a batch size of 16 and fixed the maximum number of epochs to 50, while clipping the gradient norm to 10 and using an early stopping criterion of 7 epochs. The duration of the mixture signals was set to 4 seconds during training. To ensure the convergence for each system, training continued until the system achieved optimal generalization without overfitting or underfitting, monitored through both training and validation losses and controlled by early stopping.

3.4 Two-step methods

As additional baseline systems, we have also considered two-step target speaker extraction methods based on blind source separation (see Fig. 5). In the first step, the blind source separation network aims at estimating all individual speakers in the mixture, while in the second step, one of the output signals is selected as the target speaker based on the target speaker embedding. As blind source separation network, we have considered the LSTM-based system in [7] and a system based on Conv-TasNet [9]. For the LSTM-based network, we have used a similar architecture as for the speaker separator network described in Section 3.3 but with three LSTM layers each having 600 nodes. For the Conv-TasNet network architecture, we have used the same parameters as in [9] with causal mode using cumulative layer normalization. Both blind source separation networks have been trained using the SI-SDR loss function with the same learning rate and batch size as for

Fig. 5 Two-step method for target speaker extraction using blind source separation as the first step and target speaker selection as the second step. The embedder network used in the second step is the same embedder network as in one-speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction

the speaker separator networks in Section 3.3. In order to select the estimated target speaker from the output of the blind source separation network, embedding vectors are computed for each estimated speaker and the reference speech of the target speaker using the speaker embedder network described in Section 3.2. The estimated target speaker is selected as the estimated speaker with the smallest l_2 -norm distance to the target speaker embedding. We have only trained and tested two-step target speaker extraction methods for 2-speaker mixtures (see results in Section 4.1).

4 Results and discussion

In this section, we compare the performance of the proposed speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction systems using customized LSTM cells with the baseline system using standard LSTM cells [15] and two baseline two-step methods [7, 9] based on blind source separation. As performance measures, we have utilized the signal-to-distortion ratio (SDR) [42], the scale-invariant signal-to-distortion ratio (SI-SDR) [43], the wideband perceptual evaluation of speech quality (WB-PESQ) metric [44], the DNSMOS metric [45], and the total number of parameters (computed using the torchinfo library of PyTorch).

The results are reported in three sections, depending on the data used for training and testing. In Section 4.1, both training as well as testing are performed on 2-speaker mixtures. To investigate the robustness against having more interfering speakers in the mixture during testing than during training, in Section 4.2, systems trained on 2-speaker mixtures are evaluated on 3-speaker mixtures. Finally, in Section 4.3, systems are evaluated on mixtures containing one, two, or three speakers with and without background noise when performing training on multi-condition mixtures. In Sections 4.1 and 4.2, the results are reported only in terms of SDR, while in Section 4.3, the results are reported in terms of all considered performance measures.

4.1 Evaluation on 2-speaker mixtures

For all considered methods, i.e., one-step methods using standard and customized LSTM cells (unidirectional and bidirectional mode), and baseline two-step methods (unidirectional mode), Table 2 shows the mean SDR and the total number of parameters for 2-speaker mixtures, where all systems were trained on 2-speaker mixtures. For the two-step methods, we have considered a version using the speaker embedder network to assign the target speaker and a version using oracle assignment of the target speaker. First, it can be observed that as expected the performance of the bidirectional one-step methods is larger than the performance of the unidirectional one-step methods. Second, both in unidirectional as well as bidirectional mode, the performance is significantly

Table 2 Mean SDR and total number of parameters (#Param) of baseline and proposed one-step methods (unidirectional and bidirectional mode), baseline two-step methods (unidirectional mode), and baseline two-step methods with oracle assignment of target speaker (unidirectional mode)

Systems	SDR (dB)	#Param
Mixture	0.14	-
One-step methods (unidirectional)		
Standard LSTM [15]	7.25	8.5 M
Customized LSTM (F) [16]	8.10	7.8 M
Customized LSTM (F+I)	8.24	6.1 M
Customized auxiliary-gated LSTM	9.22	9.3 M
One-step methods (bidirectional)		
Standard BLSTM [15]	8.59	15.8 M
Customized BLSTM (F) [16]	8.65	13.3 M
Customized BLSTM (F+I)	8.66	10.8 M
Customized auxiliary-gated BLSTM	9.27	16.8 M
Two-step methods (unidirectional)		
UPIT-LSTM [7]	7.74	8.6 M
Conv-TasNet [9]	7.82	5.0 M
Two-step methods - oracle assignment (unidirectional)		
UPIT-LSTM [7] - oracle	8.19	8.6 M
Conv-TasNet [9] - oracle	8.42	5.0 M

All systems are trained and evaluated on 2-speaker mixtures

improved when using customized LSTM cells instead of standard LSTM cells. When customizing both forget and input gates, the mean SDR is improved by 0.99 dB (unidirectional) and 0.07 dB (bidirectional) compared to standard LSTM cell, while the mean SDR is only improved by 0.14 dB (unidirectional) and 0.01 dB (bidirectional) compared to only customizing the forget gate. The mean SDR is further improved when using the proposed customized

Table 3 Mean SDR of baseline and proposed one-step methods (unidirectional and bidirectional mode)

Systems	SDR (dB)
Mixture	-3.05
One-step methods (unidirectional)	
Standard LSTM [15]	0.03
Customized LSTM (F) [16]	0.12
Customized LSTM (F+I)	0.32
Customized auxiliary-gated LSTM	0.66
One-step methods (bidirectional)	
Standard BLSTM [15]	0.47
Customized BLSTM (F) [16]	0.51
Customized BLSTM (F+I)	0.55
Customized auxiliary-gated BLSTM	0.89

All systems are trained on only 2-speaker mixtures and evaluated on 3-speaker mixtures

Table 4 Mean SDR, SI-SDR, WB-PESQ, and DNSMOS of baseline and proposed one-step methods (unidirectional and bidirectional mode)

Systems	2-speaker mixtures				3-speaker mixtures			
	SDR	SI-SDR	WB-PESQ	DNSMOS	SDR	SI-SDR	WB-PESQ	DNSMOS
Mixture	0.14	0.04	1.08	3.01	− 3.05	− 3.20	1.05	2.83
One-step methods (unidirectional)								
Standard LSTM [15]	8.01	7.47	1.43	3.15	2.81	2.19	1.14	2.89
Customized LSTM (F) [16]	8.17	7.92	1.73	3.27	3.03	2.88	1.26	2.95
Customized LSTM (F+I)	8.22	7.99	1.74	3.27	3.11	2.93	1.26	2.95
Customized auxiliary-gated LSTM	9.24	8.61	1.76	3.29	3.80	3.04	1.27	2.97
One-step methods (bidirectional)								
Standard BLSTM [15]	8.68	8.50	1.70	3.26	3.09	2.87	1.24	2.97
Customized BLSTM (F) [16]	8.72	8.65	1.74	3.27	3.17	3.00	1.26	2.99
Customized BLSTM (F+I)	8.72	8.66	1.74	3.27	3.17	3.01	1.26	2.99
Customized auxiliary-gated BLSTM	9.41	8.85	1.77	3.30	3.96	3.21	1.28	3.01

All systems are trained on multi-condition mixtures and evaluated on 2-speaker mixtures and 3-speaker mixtures

auxiliary-gated LSTM cells, both in unidirectional mode (1.97 dB) and bidirectional mode (0.68 dB), compared to standard LSTM cells. It can also be observed that for each proposed system, as well as for the baseline customized LSTM (F), the performance improvement when switching from unidirectional to bidirectional mode is not substantial, particularly for the customized auxiliary-gated LSTM. One possible reason is that the most crucial context information for the target speaker comes from the recent past, making future context less essential. Third, it can be observed that the performance of both two-step methods decreases when using the speaker embedder network to assign the target speaker compared to oracle assignment. The performance decreases by 0.5 dB for UPIT-LSTM and 0.6 dB for Conv-TasNet. Finally, it can be observed that both proposed one-step methods using

variants of LSTM cells outperform the baseline two-step methods for target speaker extraction.

4.2 Evaluation on 3-speaker mixtures

In this section, we investigate the effect of having more interfering speakers in the mixture during testing than during training. Since in this case two-step methods anyway do not perform well, we only consider one-step methods. Table 3 shows the mean SDR of the same one-step methods as in Section 4.1 (trained on 2-speaker mixtures) but now evaluated on 3-speaker mixtures. As expected, it can be observed that the performance of all one-step methods systematically degrades compared to the results in Table 2. This can be explained by the fact that these systems are not aware of two interfering speakers at the time of training and hence fail to generalize for such conditions.

Table 5 Mean SDR, SI-SDR, WB-PESQ, and DNSMOS of baseline and proposed one-step methods (unidirectional and bidirectional mode)

Systems	Noisy 2-speaker mixtures				Noisy 3-speaker mixtures			
	SDR	SI-SDR	WB-PESQ	DNSMOS	SDR	SI-SDR	WB-PESQ	DNSMOS
Mixture	− 4.17	− 4.35	1.04	2.55	− 6.39	− 6.66	1.04	2.50
One-step methods (unidirectional)								
Standard LSTM [15]	3.98	3.35	1.30	2.89	0.24	− 0.49	1.09	2.75
Customized LSTM (F) [16]	4.01	3.78	1.30	2.93	0.73	− 0.14	1.13	2.80
Customized LSTM (F+I)	4.04	3.81	1.31	2.93	0.73	− 0.10	1.13	2.81
Customized auxiliary-gated LSTM	4.91	4.12	1.32	2.96	0.75	− 0.16	1.14	2.83
One-step methods (bidirectional)								
Standard BLSTM [15]	4.01	3.98	1.30	2.93	0.66	− 0.14	1.11	2.80
Customized BLSTM (F) [16]	4.19	4.09	1.31	2.93	0.74	− 0.06	1.13	2.81
Customized BLSTM (F+I)	4.21	4.11	1.31	2.94	0.74	− 0.07	1.13	2.81
Customized auxiliary-gated BLSTM	5.23	4.48	1.33	2.98	0.80	− 0.05	1.13	2.83

All systems are trained on multi-condition mixtures and evaluated on 2-speaker mixtures and 3-speaker mixtures with background noise

4.3 Evaluation on multi-condition mixtures

In order to make the speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction systems more robust against multiple interfering speakers and background noise, multi-condition training can be performed. In this experiment, all considered systems are trained with 2-speaker mixtures, 3-speaker mixtures, 1-speaker mixtures with background noise (noisy 1-speaker mixtures), and 2-speaker mixtures with background noise (noisy 2-speaker mixtures). The performance is evaluated separately for 2-speaker mixtures, 3-speaker mixtures, noisy 1-speaker mixtures, and noisy 2-speaker mixtures. To investigate the robustness of the systems, the performance is also evaluated for 3-speaker mixtures with background noise (noisy 3-speaker mixtures), which is not used during training.

Similarly as before, the speech samples for training are chosen from the 100 h training set and official validation set of the Librispeech dataset [36], while the noise samples are chosen from the DNS challenge dataset [46]. To create noisy mixtures, the noise is added at an SNR which is randomly chosen between -5 and 10 dB. All together, we have generated 320 h of training data and 80 h of validation data, considering 2-speaker mixtures, 3-speaker mixtures, noisy 1-speaker mixtures, and noisy 2-speaker mixtures in equal proportion. For testing, we have generated 35 h of testing data considering 7 h for each mixture type. The speech samples are chosen from the official test set of the Librispeech dataset, while the noise samples are chosen from the MUSAN dataset [37], which makes the test set completely disjoint from the training and validation sets.

Fig. 6 Example spectrogram for the mixture signal, the target speech component, and the estimated target speech component using the customized BLSTM (F+I) and the customized auxiliary-gated BLSTM

Table 4 shows the mean SDR, SI-SDR, WB-PESQ, and DNSMOS scores for 2-speaker mixtures and 3-speaker mixtures. When using multi-condition training, the performance for 2-speaker mixtures is improved for the baseline as well as the proposed systems compared to training only on 2-speaker mixtures (see mean SDR results in Table 2). Although this is unexpected, similar results have been reported in [19]. When comparing the mean SDR results between Tables 3 and 5 for 3-speaker mixtures, it can be observed that multi-condition training significantly improves the performance for all systems. For both 2-speaker as well as 3-speaker mixtures, both proposed variants of LSTM cells show a consistent improvement in terms of all performance measures compared to standard LSTM cells and LSTM cells where only the forget gate is customized. The best performance is obtained when using the customized auxiliary-gated LSTM cells, both in unidirectional as well as bidirectional mode. To offer a more intuitive comparison between both proposed variants, Fig. 6 shows example spectrograms of the mixture signal, the target speech component in the mixture, and the estimated target speech components using the customized BLSTM (F+I) and the customized auxiliary-gated BLSTM. It can be observed that the spectrogram produced by the customized auxiliary-gated BLSTM more closely resembles the spectrogram of the target speech component, whereas the spectrogram produced by the customized BLSTM (F+I) contains more residuals from the interfering speakers.

Tables 5 and 6 show the mean SDR, SI-SDR, WB-PESQ, and DNSMOS scores for noisy 2-speaker mixtures, noisy 3-speaker mixtures, and noisy 1-speaker

Table 6 Mean SDR, SI-SDR, WB-PESQ, and DNSMOS of baseline and proposed one-step methods (unidirectional and bidirectional mode)

Systems	Noisy 1-speaker mixtures			
	SDR	SI-SDR	WB-PESQ	DNSMOS
Mixture	2.26	2.23	1.26	2.74
One-step methods (unidirectional)				
Standard LSTM [15]	12.04	11.98	2.08	3.30
Customized LSTM (F) [16]	12.54	12.03	2.22	3.31
Customized LSTM (F+I)	12.91	12.32	2.22	2.32
Customized auxiliary-gated LSTM	13.66	13.06	2.25	3.34
One-step methods (bidirectional)				
Standard BLSTM [15]	12.60	12.11	2.22	3.33
Customized BLSTM (F) [16]	12.88	12.81	2.24	3.35
Customized BLSTM (F+I)	12.98	12.79	2.24	3.35
Customized auxiliary-gated BLSTM	13.79	13.20	2.27	3.38

All systems are trained on multi-condition mixtures and evaluated on 1-speaker mixtures with background noise

mixtures. Similar to Table 4, both proposed variants of LSTM cells improve the performance compared to standard LSTM cells and LSTM cells where only the forget gate is customized (except for the mean SI-SDR for noisy 3-speaker mixtures in unidirectional mode). The performance improvement for noisy 1-speaker mixtures indicates that the proposed speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction systems can also be utilized for personalized speech enhancement. Furthermore, the performance for noisy 3-speaker mixtures shows that training on multi-condition mixtures enables the systems to generalize to these mixtures, which were not included during training. In conclusion, for all considered mixtures the best performance is obtained when using proposed customized auxiliary-gated LSTM cells, both in unidirectional as well as bidirectional mode.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed two variants of LSTM cells for the separator network of single-channel speaker-conditioned target speaker extraction systems. Aiming at retaining only information related to the target speaker, the first proposed variant customizes both the forget gate and the input gate. For the second variant, we introduced a new gate within the LSTM cell, referred to as the auxiliary-modulation gate, aiming at learning the long-term and short-term discriminative features of the target speaker. Both in unidirectional as well as bidirectional mode, experimental results on 2-speaker mixtures, 3-speaker mixtures with and without background noise, and for noisy 1-speaker mixtures show that both proposed variants of LSTM cells outperform standard LSTM cells when using multi-condition training. Overall, the best performance is obtained when using customized auxiliary-gated LSTM cells. In future work, we plan to explore the potential benefit of applying customized LSTM variants with different modalities of auxiliary information for target speaker extraction as well as for other speech processing applications, such as own voice reconstruction in hearables exploiting an in-ear microphone.

Acknowledgements

Not applicable.

Authors' contributions

The contribution of the first author consists of developing the algorithms, performing the simulations, analyzing the results, and drafting the article. The contribution of the second and third authors consists of critically discussing the developed algorithms and the simulation results with the first author and proofreading and revising the article. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Funding

Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL. The Oldenburg Branch for Hearing, Speech and Audio Technology HSA is funded in the program *ggg\$Vorab\$NII\$S\$* by the Lower Saxony Ministry of Science and Culture (MWK) and the Volkswagen Foundation for its further development.

Data availability

All datasets used during this study are publicly available and can be found at the following websites: the Librispeech dataset at <https://www.openslr.org/12>, the Voxceleb dataset at <https://www.robots.ox.ac.uk/~vgg/data/voxceleb/>, the DNS challenge dataset at <https://github.com/microsoft/DNS-Challenge>, and the MUSAN dataset at <https://www.openslr.org/17/>.

Declarations**Competing interests**

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Received: 31 May 2024 Accepted: 11 November 2024

Published online: 02 December 2024

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